

On the System of Nonlinear Rational Difference Equations

Authors : Qianhong Zhang, Wenzhuan Zhang

Abstract : This paper is concerned with the global asymptotic behavior of positive solution for a system of two nonlinear rational difference equations. Moreover, some numerical examples are given to illustrate results obtained

Keywords : difference equations, stability, unstable, global asymptotic behavior.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014